

Supplementary Materials belonging to

Safety and transfer of veterinary drugs from substrate to black soldier fly larvae

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Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1

Additional tandem mass spectrometry transitions and parameters used for quantification of the veterinary drugs subjected to the black soldier fly larvae, that were not included in a previous study (Berendsen et al., 2015). The most abundant product ions used for quantification are underlined.

Compound	Precursor ion (<i>m/z</i>)	Product ion (<i>m/z</i>)	DP (eV)	CE (eV)	CXP (eV)
Eprinomectin	936.3*	<u>490.2</u>	15	69	34
		352.1	15	73	28
Eprinomectin-d3	939.5*	355.2	15	67	12
Nigericine	747.5*	703.4	20	77	44
Salinomycin	773.4*	<u>431.1</u>	20	71	30
		531.1	20	63	38
Narasin	787.3*	<u>431.1</u>	20	75	30
		531.1	20	59	40
Toltrazuril	426.0	<u>193.0</u>	20	31	13
		114.9	20	67	13
Toltrazuril-d3	429.0	180.9	20	49	13
Toltrazuril sulfone	455.8	<u>455.8</u>	20	-5	-13
		399.1	50	-18	-17
Toltrazuril sulfone-d3	455.9	399.1	50	-18	-17

Abbreviations: DP = declustering potential; CE = collision energy; CXP = collision cell exit potential.

*Sodium adduct

Supplementary Table S2

Limit of quantification per compound for the different matrices in $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, used for analysis of the veterinary drugs that were subjected to the black soldier fly larvae through the start spiked substrate.

Compound	Spiked substrate ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Insect ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	Frass ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)
Narasin	5	1	11
Salinomycin	4	1	2
Toltrazuril	93	3	159
Toltrazuril-sulfone	-	18	250
Enrofloxacin	3	1	45
Ciprofloxacin	-	1	3
Oxytetracycline	15	7	17
Sulfamethoxazole	1	1	3
N ₄ -acetylsulfamethoxazole	-	3	10
Eprinomectin	14	8	24

Supplementary Table S3

Actual measured concentrations of spiked veterinary drugs in the substrate prior to the experiment with black soldier fly larvae, with corresponding recoveries.

Compound	Intended spike concentration (µg/kg)	Measured spike concentration substrate start (µg/kg)	Corresponding recoveries (%)
Narasin	5000-50000	3984-49316	80-99
Salinomycin	5000-50000	3966-33175	79-66
Toltrazuril	5000-50000	5449-51221	109-102
Enrofloxacin	500-5000	525-5243	105-105
Oxytetracycline	500-5000	452-4669	90-93
Sulfamethoxazole	500-5000	96-665	18-13
Eprinomectin	500-5000	572-5271	114-105

Supplementary Table S4

Details of the Dunnett's multiple comparison tests of black soldier fly larval survival and fresh weight, upon the veterinary drug exposure conditions as compared to their respective solvent control, as extracted from GraphPad Prism.

BSF larval survival						
Control	Comparison tested	Mean difference	q-value	P < 0.05	95% CI of difference	df ANOVA (treatment, residual, total)
Control CH ₃ OH	OTC-0.5	-0.6667	0.5270	No	-4.323 to 2.990	4, 10, 14
	OTC-5	2.667	2.108	No	-0.9896 to 6.323	
	SMX-0.5	-0.6667	0.5270	No	-4.323 to 2.990	
	SMX-5	0.0	0.0	No	-3.656 to 3.656	
Control DMSO	NAR-5	-1.333	0.4399	No	-10.23 to 7.562	8, 18, 26
	NAR-50	-2.000	0.6599	No	-10.90 to 6.895	
	SAL-5	-2.000	0.6599	No	-10.90 to 6.895	
	SAL-50	-2.000	0.6599	No	-10.90 to 6.895	
	TZ-5	-1.333	0.4399	No	-10.23 to 7.562	
	TZ-50	-1.333	0.4399	No	-10.23 to 7.562	
	EPR-0.5	6.000	1.980	No	-2.895 to 14.90	
	EPR-5	18.00	5.939	Yes (***)	9.105 to 26.90	
Control CH ₃ OH /NH ₃	ENROF-0.5	0.6667	0.6124	No	-2.450 to 3.783	2, 6, 8
	ENROF-5	2.000	1.837	No	-1.117 to 5.117	
Total BSF larval fresh weight						
Control	Comparison tested	Mean difference	q-value	P < 0.05	95% CI of difference	df ANOVA (treatment, residual, total)
Control blank	Control MeOH	0.01333	0.09074	No	-0.4098 to 0.4365	3, 8, 11
	Control DMSO	0.8227	5.598	Yes (*)	0.3995 to 1.246	
	Control MeOH/NH ₃	0.4037	2.747	No	-0.01950 to 0.8268	

Control CH ₃ OH	OTC-0.5	0.3720	2.353	No	-0.08489 to 0.8289	4, 10, 14
	OTC-5	0.8453	5.348	Yes (*)	0.3884 to 1.302	
	SMX-0.5	0.3883	2.457	No	-0.06856 to 0.8452	
	SMX-5	0.2390	1.512	No	-0.2179 to 0.6959	
Control DMSO	NAR-5	0.4307	1.790	No	-0.2754 to 1.137	8, 18, 26
	NAR-50	-0.06400	0.2660	No	-0.7701 to 0.6421	
	SAL-5	-0.1597	0.6637	No	-0.8657 to 0.5464	
	SAL-50	-0.5597	2.326	No	-1.266 to 0.1464	
	TZ-5	-0.4527	1.882	No	-1.159 to 0.2534	
	TZ-50	0.4293	1.785	No	-0.2767 to 1.135	
	EPR-0.5	5.048	20.98	Yes (***)	4.342 to 5.754	
	EPR-5	5.957	24.76	Yes (***)	5.251 to 6.663	
Control CH ₃ OH/NH ₃	ENROF-0.5	-0.2153	0.6759	No	-1.127 to 0.6968	2, 6, 8
	ENROF-5	0.1947	0.6110	No	-0.7174 to 1.107	

Abbreviations: DMSO = dimethylsulfoxide; BSF = black soldier fly; ENR = enrofloxacin; EPR = eprinomectin; NAR = narasin; OTC = oxytetracycline; SAL = salinomycin; SMX = sulfamethoxazole; TZ = toltrazuril, CI = confidence interval; q-value = the minimum posterior probability that H_0 is true.

Marks * and *** indicate P -value < 0.05 and < 0.001 , respectively.